

STRENGTHENING SOCIO-ECONOMIC STABILITY IN REGIONS VIA LOCAL BUDGET REVENUE AUGMENTATION

I.I. Abduganiyev

Student of Tashkent State University of Economics

Introduction

In an era of increasing economic uncertainty and regional disparities, the role of local governments in promoting socio-economic stability has never been more critical. One of the key tools at their disposal is the local budget, which can be strategically managed to foster sustainable development and stability. This article explores the topic of local budget revenue augmentation and its potential to strengthen socio-economic stability in regions.

Local budgets are the lifeblood of regional development, funding everything from infrastructure projects to social services. However, many regions struggle with limited resources, making it challenging to meet the needs of their communities. This is where the concept of revenue augmentation comes into play. By identifying and implementing strategies to increase local budget revenues, regions can enhance their capacity to support socio-economic stability.

The purpose of this article is to delve into the intricacies of local budget revenue augmentation, examining its theoretical underpinnings, practical applications, and potential impact on socio-economic stability. The objective is to provide a comprehensive understanding of this topic and offer insights that can guide policy decisions in Uzbekistan and beyond.

Current state of socio-economic stability in regions

The Uzbekistan Statistics Agency's preliminary 2023 statistics give insight on the socioeconomic standing of different regions. Each region makes a distinct economic contribution to the country, ranging from Andijan's GRP of UZS 68.2 trillion (\$5.5 billion) to Tashkent City's astounding GRP of UZS 181.9 trillion (\$14.7

billion). The economic activity, investments, and population dynamics of each region offer a thorough picture of their respective development paths.³⁹

The data on the number of newly established enterprises and organizations provides valuable insights into the entrepreneurial activity and business environment across various regions of Uzbekistan in a given period. Fergana, with 8,248 newly established entities, demonstrates robust entrepreneurial growth, possibly indicating a favorable business environment or government support for startups in the region. Tashkent city stands out significantly with 16,987 new enterprises, suggesting a vibrant and dynamic business landscape in the capital city, likely fueled by its status as the economic and financial center of the country.

Other regions with substantial numbers include Samarkand, Kashkadarya, and Tashkent region, each surpassing 7,000 new establishments. Conversely, Syrdarya, Navoi, and Surkhandarya exhibit comparatively lower figures, potentially indicating varying levels of economic development or investment attractiveness in these areas.⁴⁰

In the table below, we can see how local budgets performed during 2023

No	Regions	Forecast	Actual	%	(+;-)
	Total	52 046	55 539	106,7	3 492
1	The Republic of Karakalpakstan	2 673	2 844	106,4	170
2	Andijan province	3 741	3 931	105,1	190
3	Bukhara province	3 566	3 792	106,3	226
4	Jizzakh province	2 040	2 228	109,2	188

³⁹ Stat.uz – official website of Statistics Agency under the President of the RUz

⁴⁰ Daryo.uz (2024) Analyzing Uzbekistan’s Regional Development: Insights from 2023 Socio-Economic Data, Daryo.uz. Available at: <https://daryo.uz/en/2024/02/19/analyzing-uzbekistans-regional-development-insights-from-2023-socio-economic-data>.

5	Kashkadarya province	4 345	4 608	106,0	263
6	Navoiy province	2 823	3 039	107,7	216
7	Namangan province	3 338	3 517	105,4	179
8	Samarkand province	4 811	5 100	106,0	289
9	Surkhandarya province	2 809	3 043	108,3	234
10	Syrdarya province	1 281	1 390	108,5	109
11	Tashkent province	5 667	6 024	106,3	358
12	Fergana province	4 979	5 169	103,8	190
13	Khorezm province	2 565	2 741	106,9	176
14	Tashkent city	7 410	8 112	109,5	702

Based on the changes envisaged in the tax policy and economic growth indicators, the forecast of State budget revenues for 2024 is set at 270.6 trillion soums or 20.8 percent of the gross domestic product.

Role of local budgets in regional development

In the grand scheme of regional development, local budgets serve as a pivotal instrument. They are the financial blueprint that guides the growth and progress of a region, shaping its future and determining its socio-economic stability.

One of the most significant roles of local budgets is in the realm of infrastructure development. Infrastructure, be it roads, schools, or hospitals, forms the backbone of any region. It is the physical manifestation of development and progress. Local budgets allocate funds for the construction and maintenance of such infrastructure, thereby directly contributing to the region's development.

Moreover, local budgets finance essential public services. These services, which include education, healthcare, and social welfare, significantly contribute to

the quality of life in the region. By ensuring that these services are adequately funded, local budgets play a crucial role in promoting socio-economic stability.⁴¹

Local budgets also serve as an economic stimulus. By investing in local businesses and industries, they can stimulate economic growth and job creation. This not only boosts the region's economy but also improves the livelihoods of its residents.

Resource allocation is another critical role of local budgets. Each region has its own unique needs and priorities. Local budgets ensure that resources are allocated in a manner that addresses these specific needs, allowing for more targeted and effective development strategies.

Lastly, local budgets foster community engagement. The budgeting process provides an opportunity for local governments to engage with the community, fostering a sense of ownership and accountability. This not only makes the budgeting process more transparent but also ensures that the budget reflects the needs and aspirations of the community it serves.

Relationship between local budget revenue and socio-economic stability

Local budget revenue and socio-economic stability are intrinsically linked, with each influencing the other in a continuous, dynamic relationship. The revenue that a local government collects through various means—such as taxes, fees, and grants—is a critical resource that fuels the engine of local development and social stability.

Firstly, local budget revenue is the primary financial tool that local governments have at their disposal to provide public goods and services. These can range from infrastructure projects like roads and schools, to social services such as healthcare and welfare programs. The availability and quality of these goods and services are key determinants of the socio-economic stability of a region. They contribute to the well-being of the population, facilitate economic activity, and can help reduce inequality.

⁴¹ Meyliyev, O., 2023. Science and Innovation Ways to Increase the Revenues of Local Budgets While Ensuring the Economic Development of Regions

Secondly, local budget revenue can be seen as a barometer of the economic health of a region. High levels of revenue often indicate a robust local economy with thriving businesses and a prosperous population. This economic prosperity can, in turn, contribute to social stability by reducing unemployment and poverty rates.

However, the relationship between local budget revenue and socio-economic stability is not always straightforward. For instance, if the revenue is derived from unstable or unsustainable sources, it could lead to volatility in the provision of public goods and services. Similarly, if the revenue is not managed effectively or equitably, it could exacerbate socio-economic disparities and lead to social unrest.

Therefore, while local budget revenue is undoubtedly crucial for socio-economic stability, it is equally important to consider how this revenue is generated, managed, and distributed. A balanced and sustainable approach to local budget revenue can contribute significantly to the socio-economic stability of a region.

Innovative strategies for revenue generation and their potential impacts on socio-economic stability

In the contemporary landscape of regional development, local governments are increasingly exploring innovative strategies for revenue generation. These strategies, while diverse in nature, share a common goal: to bolster the local budget, thereby enhancing socio-economic stability in the region.

One such strategy is the issuance of green bonds. These are a type of municipal bond specifically earmarked to fund environmentally friendly or “green” projects. The dual advantage of this approach is that it not only generates revenue but also promotes sustainable development. The potential impact on socio-economic stability is significant. It can lead to job creation in green industries and contribute to environmental sustainability, thereby fostering a more resilient and prosperous community.

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) represent another innovative strategy. In a PPP, a government agency and a private sector entity collaborate to provide a public service or project. The private entity assumes substantial financial, technical, and operational risk in the project, while the public sector entity benefits from the

revenue generated. This approach can lead to improved service delivery, stimulate economic activity, and ultimately enhance socio-economic stability.⁴²

Land Value Capture (LVC) is a policy approach that enables communities to recover and reinvest land value increases that result from public investment and other government actions. By financing infrastructure and growth-related public projects that can lead to increased property values, LVC can generate significant revenue and spur regional development.

The digitalization of tax collection is another strategy that holds great promise. By implementing digital solutions for tax collection, local governments can increase efficiency, reduce corruption, and broaden the tax base. This can lead to increased revenue and improved public trust in the government, both of which are crucial for socio-economic stability.

Lastly, some local governments have experimented with voluntary contributions, asking residents for donations on top of their regular taxes. This approach can generate additional revenue and foster a sense of community involvement, thereby enhancing social cohesion and stability.

These innovative strategies for revenue generation can have a profound impact on socio-economic stability. By increasing local budget revenues, they enable local governments to invest more in public goods and services, stimulate economic activity, and foster community involvement. However, the success of these strategies can depend on a variety of factors, including the local context and the implementation process. Therefore, it's important for local governments to carefully consider these factors when exploring innovative revenue generation strategies.

⁴² Kelly, H. (2023) 8 local government revenue generation sources 2023, GovPilot. Available at: <https://www.govpilot.com/blog/local-government-revenue-generation>.

REFERENCES

1. Afonso, W., 2021. Planning for the Unknown: Local Government Strategies from the Fiscal Year 2021 Budget Season in Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic. *State and Local Government Review*
2. Hou, Y. and Seligman, J.S., 2015. Local Government Revenue Stability and Revenue Policy over Recessions
3. Meyliyev, O., 2023. Science and Innovation Ways to Increase the Revenues of Local Budgets While Ensuring the Economic Development of Regions
4. IMF, 2021. Republic of Uzbekistan: 2021 Article IV Consultation
5. Musayeva F. Sh., 2023. Effective Management of Local Budget Revenues and Expenditures in the Republic of Uzbekistan
6. Malikov T, Kobulov K. Models of market economy formation and Interaction of fiscal policy. *International Journal of Economic Growth and Environmental Issues*-ISSN.:2321-6247.
7. TS Malikov, OO Olimjonov. The merits of the ancestors in the formation and development of financial and tax science. 2021
8. Malikov TS, Jalilov PT. Budget tax policy. Tashkent. Academy. 2011.
9. Malikov T, Haydarov N. State budget. Textbook/Tashkent Financial Institute. T.:“Economics and Finance. 2007:84.